

Analysis of Coaching and Counseling in Reducing Gap of Competency to Support Career Development (Case Study at PT. MAHLE INDONESIA)

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Abstract:- Human Resources (HR) is the main capital for companies to build business competition. In order to win the business competition, surely, the company needs to excel in the quality of human resources. One of the company's efforts to build HR qualifications is by reducing the gap in competency that exists in employees. However, sometimes the methods and the way that have been used by the company are not optimal yet. This can be seen in example by the implementation of career development in the company. There’s no optimalization of career development process, indicated from promotional activities those are not running well. This condition is due to the employee are still considered not meet their competency standards yet, indicated by the results of employee performance appraisal whereas still indicated the presence gap of competency. This research is studying how company can make improvements in reducing the gap of competency, through optimization of coaching and counseling. Using qualitative methods and data analysis is by Nvivo, the final result of this research is to find a model concept of coaching and counseling in reducing gap of competency of employee to support the optimization on career development in the company PT. MAHLE Indonesia.

Keywords:- Coaching & Conseling, Gap Competency, Career Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

HR is considered as the most important asset in a company, because individuals or humans are able to move all the components in an organization or company. Humans are resources that have thoughts and feelings, this is what distinguishes them from other factors of production. With these differences in character and their very important roles, organizations or companies must always manage their production factors effectively and efficiently, in order to be able to create superior goods or services.

An organization or company essentially also utilizes the competencies possessed by individuals to develop their careers. The organization will create opportunities for all individuals, so that they continue to develop, so that they can realize their full potential and develop their career paths. These individuals are required to develop and realize their abilities

and competencies to the fullest so as to support the achievement of individual effectiveness, which then encourages the effectiveness of an organization in achieving its goals.

Implementation coaching and counseling, will also make better organizational behavior so that company goals will be achieved. However, in actualization there are still many companies that do not optimally involve the process coaching and counseling This is in the process of human resource management, especially to support the career paths of its employees [1][2][3].

PT. MAHLE Indonesia is a manufacturing company whose business line is producing automotive parts, this company is located in the GIIC Industrial Area, Deltamas, Cikarang. The company had the same thing happen. Until now, with a workforce of 66 (sixty six) people relying on technological support and the ability of employees to be able to master several skills in their operations, of course to carry out this strategy requires employees with adequate competence.

Based on company data, in the last 5 (five) years, there has been 1 (one) promotion for employees at level staff and supervisor.

Tahun	Jumlah Promosi pada Level Staff dan Supervisor	Proses yang Dilakukan dalam Promosi				
		Penilaian atas Kebutuhan Organisasi	Penilaian atas Kinerja Karyawan	Penilaian atas Tugas Khusus	Penilaian berdasarkan Aspek Psikologis	Coaching dan Counseling
2017	0	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak
2018	3	Ya	Ya	Ya	Ya	Tidak
2019	0	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak
2020	0	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak
2021	0	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak	Tidak

Fig 1 : Promotion Data at staff and supervisor level PT. MAHLE Indonesia for the last 5 (five) years

In addition, from the results of the employee performance appraisal company PT. MAHLE Indonesia based appraisal which is carried out every 1 (once) year, there are still several employees whose competency levels are not in accordance with the standards. The results of employee assessments indicate the presence gap competency, identified

and followed up or intervened only with procurement in-house training, as shown in the Skill Matrix form as follows:

PT. MAHLE INDONESIA		Doc	INI-F-MR-001	
SKILL MATRIX		Version	6.0	
		Date	2/2/2020	
		Page	1 to 2	
POSITION	Controlling SPV	Employee Name		
DEPT	Finance & Controlling	Job Date Update	2-Jun-20	
COMPETENCY	STANDARD COMPETENCY	MATRIX COMPETENCY	GAP ANALYSIS	TREATMENT
FUNCTIONAL COMPETENCY				
1 Accounting Knowledge proficiency	3	3	0	
2 SAP (FI/CO) and MS Office, especially excel	3	3	0	
3 Understand MAHLE (MAHLE Advance Reporting Systems)	4	4	0	
4 Fluently in English	3	2	-1	INHOUSE TRAINING
5 Financial Report Analysis	4	3	-1	INHOUSE TRAINING
6 Policy Development	4	3	-1	INHOUSE TRAINING
CORE COMPETENCY				
1 Self Management (Self awareness & feedback, Continuous learning, Resiliency)	3	3	0	
2 Collaboration (Communication, Networking & Knowledge sharing, Diversity & inclusive mindset)	3	2	-1	INHOUSE TRAINING
3 Change & Innovation (Change Mindset, Innovation Focus, Acceptance of uncertainty)	3	3	0	
4 Performance Orientation (Responsibility, Solution Orientation, Efficiency)	3	3	0	
5 Value Creation (Holistic Thinking, Customer Value add, Market Orientation)	3	3	0	
<small>If in one position there is more than one employee please add page/for detail see page add/for detail see for person at MAHLE terdapat halaman</small>				
Qualifications : 0-1: Unacceptable, poor, much less than acceptable Tidak dapat diterima, buruk, lebih dari tidak dapat diterima 2: Weak, less than acceptable Lemah, kurang dapat diterima 3: Good, acceptable, satisfactory average Baik, dapat diterima, rata-rata memuaskan 4: Very good, full performance behaviours, above average Sangat baik, berkinerja penuh, diatas rata-rata 5: Excellent, exceptional, mastery, much more than acceptable Baik sekali, luar biasa, mahir, lebih dari dapat diterima				
HOD Dept		HR & GA Dept	Employee	

Fig 2 : Skill Matrix for Controlling Supervisor Position

According to the management, the intervention has not been optimal in minimizing gap competency and development. The previous research has discussed coaching and counseling including:

- Coaching and counseling more associated with employee performance [1] [2].
- Research on competency with motivation and employee's engagement [3], as well as on the relationship between competency and employee satisfaction and motivation [4].
- Research on coaching associated with career development through leadership [5].

Particularly, researchers will make observations on the employee promotion process as an indicator of the implementation of the career development process, whereas promotions are expected to implement more effectively with reductions of gap competency that still occurs in the employees. When the competency gap has been eliminated, then the competencies of employees can be meet in accordance with the requirements, thus career development will be effectively implemented and works well. This effectiveness can have an impact to keep the sustainability of the organization.

II. LITERATURE

A. Coaching & Conseling

Coaching is a briefing process carried out by superiors/seniors to train and provide orientation to their subordinates about optimal workplace realities. Coaching more to do with improved skill. By applying the method coaching, basically is beneficial to two parties, namely leaders and followers (bosses and subordinates), for the

organization or company as well as employees. Coaching seen as an effective method for responding to the changing and growing needs and demands of tasks and also very effective for correcting and developing performance for workers [6].

Employee counseling can reduce problems that arise at work and also improve interpersonal relations, togetherness, reconciliation and also reduce the level of depression in employees in addition to achieving an increase in a conducive work environment that will have an impact on work productivity. career direction functions to help employees to be able to realize their career planning into reality, namely by establishing the career they want and arranging the steps that must be taken to make it happen. This can be done with two approaches, namely career counseling and career information services [7].

B. Gap Competency

The competencies required for a particular job depend on many factors. Such factors include social culture, nature of business, business environment, organizational culture, work environment, organizational structure, duties and responsibilities, nature of processes and assignment of activities, attitudes and motives of colleagues, superiors and subordinates. Some of these factors might change over time and thus change the competency requirements for the same job position in the organization [8].

Gap analysis towards competency includes determining the level of proficiency required and also determining the current level of proficiency of employees. So that gap competency occurs when there is a gap between a current employee's proficiency level that is below the required level of proficiency. A competency gap generally refers to a lack of skills needed to meet job requirements. This can be measured both objectively and subjectively both from the perspective of employers and employees [9].

C. Career Development

Career development (career development) is a personality improvement that is carried out by someone to achieve a career plan and improvement by the personnel department to achieve a work plan in accordance with the path or level of the organization [10]. Career development is the process of individuals developing their strengths and applying them to their career decision-making or workplace occupations [11]. Career development basically has benefits that include:

- Improve the ability of employees. Career development through education and training will further enhance the intellectual abilities and skills of employees which can be contributed to the organization;
- Increase the supply of capable employees. The number of employees with higher capabilities than before will increase, making it easier for the leadership (management) to place employees in more appropriate jobs. Thus, the supply of employees who are capable increases and will clearly benefit the organization [12].

III. RESEARCH AND METHODS

The research design in this study is qualitative with a case study approach. Case study research (case study) is studying the interaction between variables with each other. In the end, this study aims to study how the conditions career development what happened at PT. MAHLE Indonesia and learn how coaching and counseling can contribute to the process by decreasing gap in competency that exists in employees.

The sampling method used in this study is purposive sampling, while the sampling technique or sampling technique/informants use snowball random sampling. This is because the researcher took 5 (five) participants with certain conditions to obtain the data, but if in the process it turns out that the data taken is not sufficient, then the researcher can take data from other participants, so that more complete data is obtained.

Data collection techniques are divided into three ways, namely interviews, observation, and document analysis. Interviews were conducted with informants who have a direct

relationship in implementation. In this semi-structured interview activity, the researcher used a notebook and a cell phone recording device. In addition, researchers used observation techniques participant observation (participatory observation). In this case, the researcher participates in the lives of the participants being studied. Furthermore, the researcher used this activity as secondary data collection. This secondary data was obtained by the researcher from the results of previous research, then also books, writings and scientific papers related to the topic under study.

For data processing, researchers used a software application, namely Nvivo 12 Plus for windows. Nvivo is a software package that works in a broadly similar way Microsoft Office, which was developed specifically for qualitative data analysis. Nvivo helps organize a variety of source materials, including audio recordings. As for in NVivo, the resulting analysis is Pearson The coefficient, which is used to determine whether there is a relationship between the variables and the informant's answers. From the results of the explanation above, the framework used in this research h is briefly as follows:

Fig 3 : Conceptual Framework

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This research begins with direct observation in the field, namely PT. MAHLE Indonesia, researchers also carried out one of the data analysis activities, namely regarding research items by obtaining data from the authorities in the company. Then, the researcher conducted interviews with 5 (five) people who were included as key informants, using an interview protocol. After obtaining the interview data, the researcher confirmed the correlation of the informant's answers to see the level of linearity using NVivo. If there are answers that are not in accordance with the focus of the research, then the data is reduced.

From the data search results to view similarity (similarity) between sources, seen as above. Coefficient value Pearson from the results of the NVivo analysis, it has points between 0.57 (Strong enough) to 0.76 (Strong), thus the researcher can state that by finding that the informant's answers have a level of linearity and focus, then all of the informant's answers will be used for further analysis and there is no discarded answer (because of reduction).

Then the researcher compared the answers between informants as a follow-up step of analysis, as a form of triangulation significant others. The researcher took keywords from the informants' answers to get conclusions regarding the similarity of the answers to the phenomena that the researcher wanted to know about.

After the researchers compared and categorized information on all the informants' answers, the next step was to enter the data into the Nvivo program to get 'nodes'. Then create nodes, researchers conduct data analysis to answer the existing set of problem formulations. The data source, which is an interview transcript, is imported into the NVivo 12 software for analysis.

Fig 4: Imported Data Sources on Nvivo 12

After all the data was imported into NVivo, the researcher coded the existing data. Apart from that, the researcher also conducted data reduction by looking at the most frequently discussed topics from all the data that had been imported into NVivo. From the results Word Frequency Query NVivo 12 based on imported data source, word aligned with coaching and training, appeared as much as 1.84% of all

research data sources. Then said development, training which appeared as much as 1.45%. The third level is words competency which appeared as much as 1.26% of the entire data. The following figure shows the results of the most frequently discussed word searches during interviews with respondents.

Fig 5 : Percentage Summary of Most Frequently Discussed Words

Words that are often discussed during interview sessions are known from data processing using features word cloud available on NVivo. The following picture shows world cloud of the 30 (thirty) words that are the most dominant in this research data source.

Fig 6 : Word Cloud 30 (Tiga Puluh) The most dominant word

Level conditions competency (competence) employees at PT. MAHLE Indonesia has been assessed at least once a year, through employee assessment (performance assessment). From the results of this assessment, it can be seen the level of competence possessed by each individual. As stated by the respondents, gap competency still always found in employees of PT. MAHLE Indonesia. This is because in addition to individual ability limits, the level of competence required in a position can change according to organizational needs.

As for the actions taken in the company to overcome the existence gap competency so far is training, good internal training non external training, where training It also involves third parties in its implementation. As stated by the respondents, that action training alone is not enough to reduce gap competency exist, but it is hoped that there will be other actions that are structured and programmed, as well as in synergy with training, which will be able to increase employee competency. In other words,gap competency will be reduced.

Referring to what was conveyed by the Director of PT. MAHLE Indonesia, that employee competencies that are fulfilled, will make it easy for the company to bring its employees to achieve company goals and targets, even for the next 5 (five) years, in accordance with the company's strategic plan. Therefore, the company's management expects a program that is more effective in reducing gap competency his employees.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

A. Implementation and optimization of Coaching & Counseling

Activity coaching and counseling at PT. MAHLE Indonesia so far has not been implemented optimally. Communication and direction (if it can be referred to as coaching simple level), only limited to communication between direct superiors and subordinates in an annual activity called the Annual Employee Dialogue, which is in the form of a discussion one on one between employees and their superiors directly, as well as daily communication between the two parties. Whereas coaching and counseling officially and professionally, has not been carried out routinely.

Meanwhile from word tree it was revealed that the respondents expected that coaching and counseling which are carried out even better, in a structured and organized manner and in synergy with training, will be effective to reduce gap competency employee. Another thing that was revealed was the respondent stated that coaching that is carried out internally will be more effective because it is more on target, moreover it is carried out cross-functionally to gain knowledge about matters that are the main responsibility of other departments.

Other information revealed that recently, at PT. MAHLE Indonesia has just started Individual Development Program (IDP), which aims to prepare employee candidates who will be promoted to higher positions. In this IDP project, functions coaching and counseling more structured and organized. However, it doesn't exist yet review significant regarding effectiveness coaching and counseling ongoing.

B. Implementation of Coaching & Counseling in support of Career Development

Career development as the main subject of discussion, at PT. MAHLE Indonesia is still not running optimally, especially in the last 5 (five) years. This was revealed from word tree which exists. This phenomenon was also found by researchers, using indicators of how often employee

promotions occur. Where in the last 5 (five) years there has only been a promotion for employees at this company.

Promotion of employees means that there is potential talent whose competencies are fulfilled in the current position, even have several competencies for higher positions/positions.

From word tree it was also revealed that the statements of the respondents were related career development is something that can be realized properly and optimally if previously there was a competency fulfillment process, or a minimization process gap competency, namely through implementation coaching and counseling.

B. Implementation of Coaching & Counseling in reducing Gap competency to support Career development

As shown in the word tree, respondents stated that the program coaching and counseling optimally will help reduce the competency gap. Coaching and counseling Optimal activities are activities that are planned, structured, routine and can match organizational goals. Coaching and counseling can also be implemented in conjunction with training.

Training can improve employee performance which in turn can improve employee career development as well. Companies that often hold training for employees will improve employee performance and employees will be more motivated to work so that company goals can be achieved. When done coaching and counseling to employees, then the final result is expected gap competency concerned can be identified properly and can be minimized, so in other words that the employee's competence increases.

With an increase in competence, these employees can develop themselves, and can even be planned career development against him. It is not impossible, with adequate competence, even these employees can be submitted for promotion programs in carrying out certain tasks according to the required competencies.

Finally, based on the conditions above, the researcher draws conclusions regarding the implementation coaching and counseling in reducing gap competency to support career development, with the concept model as follows.

Fig 7 : Coaching and Counseling model in reducing gap competency to support Career development

The model description above shows that coaching and counseling can identify in detail gap competency that exists, then directly helps to minimize it so that it can occur career development to the employee concerned. This can also be done in conjunction with training. Coaching and counseling can also directly support implementation career development

optimally within an organization, by increasing the motivation of employees who do not have gap competency for his position.

Related coaching and counseling used in assisting the achievement of organizational goals in the field career development. Organizational coaching is a customized individual training intervention [13]. Meanwhile, the integrative coaching model suggested in this review brings together strategies and techniques taken from 3 (three) evidence-based interventions, namely Cognitive Behavioral Coaching (CBC), Motivational Interviewing (MI) and Mindfulness that can be used together to meet the explicit needs of organizational development. By designing a coaching program and ultimately helping organizational coaches to be more effective in facilitating the achievement of the goals set. Thus, giving coaching and counseling towards employees is one of the right methods in organizational development [14].

The effect of training on work performance and career development by mediating work motivation. This research deals with training, job performance, career development and motivation [15]. Hypothesis testing shows that training has an effect on motivation at PT. Tamarind significantly. That is, the more often the supervisor conducts training for employees, the greater the motivation possessed by these employees. Conversely, if training is rarely carried out by superiors, then employee motivation will also decrease.

Both of these studies support the results of this study, where coaching and counseling considered effective in digging in more detail about gap competency existing employees, so that with a more structured and organized method and implementation, it will increase employee competency. Then with increased employee competence, then the plan career development in accordance with organizational targets in well implemented.

Also based on this research, further research can be carried out in the form of quantitative research as follows.

Proposition 1: coaching and counseling effect on gap competency

Proposition 2: coaching and counseling effect on career development

Proposition 3: gap competency effect on career development

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The results showed that activity coaching and counseling at PT. MAHLE Indonesia has not run optimally. In addition, the company is not yet optimal in utilizing the activity coaching and counseling as a means to be able to support its occurrence career development. Next, there is implementation career development at PT. MAHLE Indonesia has not run optimally. Lastly, the model formulated from this research is that coaching and counseling can reduce presence gap competency. With less gap competency, for career development can run optimally. Thus the model presented is coaching and counseling reduce gap competency and support career development.

Related gap competency, top management should consider using other methods training in following up gap competency existing in employees. For coaching and counseling, implementation can be followed by training and should be implemented in a structured and organized manner so that it is more optimal. Related career development, management should create programs for employee development, so that employees can have the opportunity to develop their careers (career development). Future research can dig deeper and wider in proving the concept of the model described in this study.

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